

FAN VA INNOVATSIYA

(Ilmiy-uslubiy to‘plam)

(“Nodavlat ta’lim muassasalarida ta’lim sifatini oshirish va talabalarning ma’naviy-ma’rifiy qiyofasini yuksaltirishning dolzarb masalalari” mavzusiga bag‘ishlanib Angren universitetida 2023-yilning dekabr oyida o‘tkazilgan Respublika konferensiyasi materiallari)

Mazkur to‘plam Angren universiteti Ilmiy kengashining 2023-yil 22-dekabr kuni o‘tkazilgan majlisi 10-son qarori bilan nashrga tavsiya etilgan.

Toshkent, “Fan ziyosi” nashriyoti, 2024-yil.

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«Fan va innovatsiya» Ilmiy-uslubiy to'plam
– Toshkent: “Fan ziyosi” nashriyoti, 2024-yil, 366 bet.

Ushbu kitob Angren shahrida joylashgan yangi universitet va boshqa OTM lar professor-o'qituvchilari va iqtidorli talabalari olib borayotgan ilmiy va ilmiy-uslubiy izlanishlar sajiyasidan darak beruvchi maqola va tezislarning majmui sanaladi. Undan o'rta umumiy ta'lim va oliy ta'limning bugungi kunda dolzarb bo'lib turgan metodik muammolari hamda ularni hal qilishning innovatsion pedagogik yechimlari, shuningdek, hozirgi zamon kishisi uchun zarur madaniy ko'nikmaga aylanib borayotgan kitobxonlikning ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ahamiyatiga doir maqolalar o'rin olgan.

To'plam oliy o'quv yurtlarining professor-o'qituvchilari, magistrant va talabalari hamda keng ilmiy jamoatchilik uchun mo'ljallangan.

Maqolalarning yangiligi, ilmiy hamda uslubiy saviyasi va keltirilgan raqam va ma'lumotlarning aniqligi uchun mualliflar mas'ul.

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KITOBSEVARLIK - YUKSAK MA'NAVIY FAZILAT

**MAMLAKATIMIZDA KITOBXONLIK AN'ANALARINI
YUKSALTIRISHNING AYRIM TASHKILY-HUQUQIY MASALALARI**

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Keyingi yillarda mamlakatimiz turli sohalar bo'yicha dunyo reytinglarda ijobiy tarafga, yuqori o'rinlarga ko'tarilishiga erishildi. Xalqaro maydonda O'zbekiston, uning tinib-tinchimas Davlat rahbari nomi bot-bot takrorlanmoqda.

Ammo, bir ziyoliy inson sifatida mamlakatimizga dahldor bitta ko'rsatkichdan rosti uyalib ketdim. Jahonning eng kitobsevar davlatlari qatorida O'zbekistonni topa olmadim. Xalqaro madaniyat indeksiga ko'ra, "Dunyoda eng ko'p kitob o'qiydigan aholiga ega mamlakat" degan mezon bo'yicha kuchli 26 davlat reytingida Hindiston birinchi o'rinni egallabdi. Bu davlatda odamlar kitob mutolaasi uchun haftasiga o'rtacha 10 soatu 42 daqiqa sarflar ekan

Reyting ro'yxatida, 9 soatu 24 daqiqa ko'rsatgich bilan Tailand ikkinchi, sakkiz soat natija bilan Xitoy uchinchi o'ringa munosib ko'rilibdi.

Shu ro'yxatning keyingi pog'analarini Filippin (7:36), Misr (7:30), Chexiya (7:24), Rossiya (7:06), Shvesiya (6:54), Fransiya (6:54), Vengriya (6:48), Saudiya Arabistoni (6:48), Polsha (6:30), Venesuela (6:24), Janubiy Afrika Respublikasi (6:18), Avstraliya (6:18), Indoneziya (6:00), Argentina (5:54), Turkiya (5:54), Ispaniya (5:48), Kanada (5:48), Germaniya (5:42), AQSh (5:42), Italiya (5:36), Braziliya (5:12), Yaponiya (4:06), Janubiy Koreya (3:06) davlatlari egallagan. Tadqiqotlar bu davlatlarning aholisi haftada kamida bitta kitob o'qishini ko'rsatgan.

Xo'sh bizda-chi? Oddiy kishilarni qo'yib turaylik, hatto ziyolilarning katta qismi bir oyda bitta kitob o'qiydimi? O'quvchilar, talabalarchi? Kun sayin ko'payib kelayotgan mulkdorlar, tadbirkorlar qatlami kitob o'qishga vaqt topayaptimi? Umuman, bizda aholining kitobxonlik darajasini tadqiq qiladigan, kitobxonlik saviyamizni o'rganadigan tashkilot yoki mas'ul idora bormi? Bor bo'lsa, ularning tahlillari qani? Hisobotlari nega e'lon qilinmaydi? Bu borada ahvolni o'nglashga oid tavsiyalari qani?

Axir biz ilmi-urfon samosini zabt etgan, dunyo tamadduniga o'zining munosib hissasini qo'shgan buyuk ajdodlar – kitobxonlikda tengi yo'q ulug' zotlarning zurriyotlarimiz-ku! Yurtimizda kitobxonlik an'anasini yuksaltirish, aholining kitobga mehrini oshirish uchun bizga nima halaqit berayapti, nima yetishmayapti?

Ikkinchi bo'lim.

FALSAFA VA MA'NAVIYAT - JAMIYAT KO'ZGUSI.

SOTSIAL BILIMLARNING FALSAFIY- METODOLOGIK ASPEKTLARI

Normo'minova N. D., Angren universiti o'qituvchisi

Philosophical-methodological aspects of social knowledge

Annotation: Scientific knowledge of society, culture and man is based on a rational basis. Methodological aspects of the process of scientific social cognition are discussed.

Keywords: scientific rationality; methodology; principles; social cognition; values; openness; complexity; social responsibility of science.

The new quality of post-non-classical rationality includes in cognition the value-target structural characteristics of the object, taking into account the contradictory nature of the human value world. The value systems are defined by the authors both as well-developed ideologies, religious systems, and as fuzzy sets of principles reflecting the system of views on the world, cognized and realized by their bearer during the evolution of his self-consciousness in a group or subculture. The fractal-evolutionary methodological approach based on the universal laws of the development of life and the nature of consciousness is considered as a methodological basis for the study of social systems and the foundation of cross-disciplinary synthesis of knowledge.

And although modern science has largely "come out of the diapers" of theology, it differs significantly within itself in its different branches, is characterized not only and even not so much (if we consider and compare it with individual humanities disciplines) by other ways of cognition than in theology, but, more importantly, by a different ratio of formal and informal institutions that determine the processes of development of scientific and theological thought. Thus, scientific rationality in the natural and exact sciences, characterized by a certain degree of evidence based on the concept of a reproducible experiment, although it differs from that of the social and humanitarian sciences, characterized only by a certain degree of persuasiveness, as an explicit general includes the desire to understand the surrounding world, which the subject of the cognition process seeks to share with others, having recorded in writing its next increment, designed to help in the end to better answer this or that question "how?". Despite all the differences from applied fundamental sciences, driven largely by the researcher's passion for knowledge and answering the question "why?", in the end, like applied sciences, still serve to get answers to the question "how?", which is backed by the customer, the nature of which affects the degree of social responsibility

or irresponsibility of science as a producer of knowledge. In contrast to science, theology, which primarily answers the questions "why?" and "why?" and designed to guide human behavior, is initially based on the acceptance of truths on faith, and the knowledge recorded in sacred written sources in a variety of religious systems may give priority to oral higher knowledge and interpretations of prescribed truths transmitted to the chosen by word of mouth. It is this feature of it that makes it almost impossible for scientists and theologians to have a dialogue, but still, the more fragile the human world becomes — social systems and ecosystems as a whole — the more aggressively representatives of religions manifest themselves in attempts to influence public life and, moreover, even to redraw state borders and the further science advances in ways and the results of cognition, the more cautiously representatives of the latter should make judgments about the impossibility of such a dialogue.

The features of modern scientific social cognition are primarily due to the basis of this process — the methodological basis that determines the horizon of understanding and the core of the relationship of scientific theories that guide the specific process of cognition of the selected object through the prism of the corresponding set of basic principles that model the world picture. Thus, the synergetic scientific school's approach to understanding a new type of rationality, largely shared by the authors, takes into account non-linearity, openness, disequilibrium and other properties of reality.

Secondly, in the process of social cognition, it is important not only to know, but also to understand. The latter means to explain and realize the very basic principles that form the paradigm of key ideas, hypotheses, reasoning and variants of conclusions underlying the new knowledge about the social object and the subject of cognition. It is the paradigmatic principles of the key ideas and concepts underlying the process of cognition that determine the boundaries of understanding obtained as a result of it.

Thirdly, the new rationality means the expansion of the field of reflection, takes into account the correlation of the characteristics of the acquired knowledge about the object not only with the peculiarity of the means and operations of the activity, but also with its value-target structures. Values are somewhat irrational. They represent some ultimate guidelines of the actors, vectors by which the subjects compare the desirability of their actions, a generalized idea of the future and acceptable ways to achieve it.

A system of values can be a detailed ideology or religious system, and a set of principles that characterize and define the norm of behavior, reflecting a system of views on the world that is not set in a clear way, but is cognized and realized by its bearer during the evolution of his self-consciousness in the process of communications and interactions in a particular group and subculture.

Fourth, the idea of openness extends to the processes of intercultural dialogue, communication and access to the information space, which requires inclusion in the consideration of cultural patterns, the dialogue of cultures. The modern information age and the intensity of communications adds the need to take into account the differences of interacting subjects when learning, since they initiate the manifestation of the characteristic features of chaos in public life. A person in conditions of unknown uncertainty loses his support, the usual order of interactions, he is forced to look for a solution, a temporary order or a prototype of it. These processes are becoming one of the essential reasons for the increasing complexity of social systems. And this constantly generated complexity creates the basis for both the chaoticization of public life and the formation of a new order.

In view of the above, studies related to the manifestations of changes in a social system far from equilibrium should be based on the understanding of society as such a system, heterogeneous, open, complex, interacting with the surrounding context. Sociological analysis should take into account both this complexity and the speed of social dynamics. New phenomena are considered as a property of the time of social change, and if a certain limit of the situation is reached, the phenomenon under study becomes the source of the next wave of social changes. The type and nature of the response of social institutions to these challenges can be considered as a sign characterizing the dominant management paradigm. In such studies, it is difficult to do without the use of a flexible integral approach, which includes the definition of the basic theoretical basis of the research program and its gradual completion, taking into account the data obtained during the study.

As a result, a hypothesis, a concept is gradually recreated, built up, and then a theory of a specific phenomenon, phenomenon or emerging social institution observed in the dynamics of changing stages of life activity.

The problem of implementing this approach, on the one hand, is in presenting scenarios through signs and indicators, and on the other hand, in justifying the methods of selecting units of analysis and subsequent determination of data collection methods, their systematization, complementarity of the data obtained, generalization of cases and description of types of social practices.

The study of the mechanism of development of the social system on the basis of a new methodology of scientific rationality — the fractal-evolutionary approach allows us to identify the possibilities and features of the multidimensional development and harmonization of communications between different levels of social structures, including between individuals. This allows us to accumulate the potential for the development of the entire society, and new opportunities for finding ways and

methods of coordinating institutions that determine the development of science and education — to ensure the processes of mutual understanding of meanings.

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FUTUROLOGIYAGA FALSAFIY-METODOLOGIK YONDASHISHNING AHAMIYATI

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Annontatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada jamiyat taraqqiyotini prognozlashning falsafiy metodologik ahamiyati haqida fikr yuritilgan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Jamiyat, taraqqiyot, innovatsiya, falsafa, iqtisod, nazariya, davlat, metodologik.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается философско-методологическая значимость прогнозирования развития общества.*

Ключевые слова: *общество, развитие, инновации, философия, экономика, теория, государство, методология.*

Annontation: *This article discusses the philosophical and methodological significance of predicting the development of society.*

Key words: *society, development, innovations, philosophy, economics, theory, state, methodology.*

Jamiyat tushunchasi. Jamiyat hayoti asrlar osha olimlar va faylasuflarning tadqiqot ob’ekti bo‘lib kelmoqda. U turli fanlar, chunonchi: sotsiologiya, tarix, siyosatshunoslik, huquqshunoslik, etnografiya, iqtisodiy nazariya va hokazolar doirasida o‘rganiladi. Muayyan fanlardan farqli o‘laroq, falsafaning vazifasi tarixiy jarayonning umumiy jihatlarini o‘rganishdan iborat. Falsafa muayyan hodisalarning

sabablari nimada degan savolga javob topish vazifasini o'z oldiga qo'ymasada, tarix fanining metodologik asoslarini yaratadi, mazkur sabablarni aniqlashga nisbatan qanday yondashish kerak, degan savolga javob beradi. U dunyoqarashga doir o'z mo'ljallariga tayanadi, ijtimoiy va gumanitar fanlarning kategoriyalar apparatini ishlab chiqishda ishtirok etadi. O'z kategoriyalarining ijtimoiy mazmunini yoritir ekan, falsafa shunga asoslanib muayyan-tarixiy jarayonlarni tahlil qilishni amalga oshiradi. Tarix falsafasining muammolaridan biri bu tarixiy jarayonning birligi muammosi va tarixni davriylashtirish tamoyillarini belgilashdir.

Falsafaning vazifasi jamiyat hayotining asosiy negizlarini, uning tizim tashkil etadigan omillarini aniqlashdan iborat. Jamiyat — tabiatning bir qismi, ya'ni ijtimoiy borliq bo'lib, odamlar uyushmasining mahsus shakli, kishilar o'rtasida amal qiladigan juda ko'plab munosabatlar yig'indisi, degan turlicha ta'riflar ham bor. Jamiyat muttasil ravishda rivojlanuvchi, takomillashib boruvchi murakkab tizimdir. Har bir yangi davrda jamiyat mohiyatini bilish zarurati vujudga keladi. Milliy mustaqillik tufayli jamiyat mohiyatini yangicha idrok etish ehtiyoji paydo bo'ldi. Prezident Islom Karimovning qator asarlarida jamiyat mohiyatini yangicha tushunishning uslubiy asoslari yaratildi.

Jamiyat moddiy va ma'naviy omillar birligidan iborat. Hozirga qadar adabiyotlarda moddiy va ma'naviy hayot bir-biridan keskin farqlanar edi. Moddiy hayot tadqiqiga ko'proq e'tibor berilar. Holbuki, jamiyatning tub mohiyati uni tashkil etuvchi inson mohiyati bilan uzviy bog'liq. Huddi inson tanasini uning ruhidan ajratib bo'lmagani singari, jamiyatning moddiy va ma'naviy jihatlarini ham bir-biridan ajratish va ularning birini ikkinchisidan ustun qo'yish mantiqqa ziddir. Prezident Islom Karimov asarlarida jamiyatning moddiy va ma'naviy manfaatlarini uyg'unlashtirish ijtimoiy taraqqiyot asosi ekani ta'kidlangan. Inson ma'naviyatini yuksaltirish orqaligina iqtisodiy rivojlanishga erishish mumkin. Shuning uchun ham hozirgi davrda aholi ma'naviyatini yuksaltirishga, milliy G'oya va mafkura asoslarini shakllantirishga katta e'tibor berilyapti. Zero, kishilar iqtisodiy jihatdan qashshoq bo'lgani uchun ilmsiz bo'lmaydi, balki, aksincha — ilmsiz bo'lgani uchun qashshoq bo'ladi. Shuning uchun yurtimizda halq ma'naviyatini yuksaltirish orqali iqtisodiy farovonlikni ta'minlashga katta e'tibor berilyapti.

Jamiyatning vujudga kelishi. Kishilarni oila bo'lib, jamoa bo'lib uyushishga nima majbur qilgan, degan masala qadim zamonlardanoq ulug' mutafakkirlar e'tiborini jalb etgan. Bu masalani diniy tushunish — uni ilohiy kuch, hudo bilan bog'lab izohlashdir.

Dunyoviy qarashlarga ko'ra, odamlar o'zlarining moddiy va ma'naviy ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun birgalikda yashashga, jamoa bo'lib birlashishga ko'nikkan. Kishilar hayotiy tajriba, aql va tafakkur tufayli jamiyat bo'lib yashashning

qulay, afzal va zarurligini tushungan. Bu jarayonda o'zaro munosabatlarga kirishgan kishilar ana shu munosabatlarni takomillashtirish, yanada rivojlantirish orqali ma'naviy kamolotga erishgan. Bu kishilarni bir-biri bilan yaqinlashtirgan, moddiy va ma'naviy ehtiyojlarini qondirish imkonini bergan.

Ijtimoiy munosabatlarning amal qilish jarayonida odamlarni uyushtirishning tarixiy shakllari — oila, davlat, jamoa (qishloq, shahar) vujudga kelgan. Odamlar o'rtasida amal qiladigan ahloqiy, diniy, ilmiy, falsafiy, huquqiy, iqtisodiy, mafkuraviy kabi munosabatlarning barchasi bir so'z bilan ijtimoiy munosabatlar deyiladi. Ijtimoiy uyushmalar kishilarning moddiy va ma'naviy ehtiyojlarini qoldirishga yordam beradi. Ular mohiyatan inson va jamiyat mavjudligining zarur sharti hisoblanadi. Masalan, oila, davlat, ta'lim-tarbiya, mahalla, Vatan kabi qadriyatlarisiz inson va jamiyat o'z mohiyatini yo'qotadi.

Insonning moddiy ehtiyojlari oziq-ovqatlar, kiyim-kechak, uy-joy, transport vositalari, o'zini himoyalash, zurriyot qoldirish kabilardan iboratdir. Ma'naviy ehtiyojlarga olamni bilish, o'zlikni anglash, dunyoqarash, donishmandlikka intilish, bilim, san'at, G'oya, mafkura go'zallik bilan, ma'naviy kamolot yo'lidagi intilishlar kiradi. Insonning asl mohiyati moddiy ehtiyojlarni madaniy shakllarda qondirilishida yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. Inson aqlli mavjudot sifatida moddiy ehtiyojlarini madaniy shakllarda qondirish uchun tabiat va jamiyat mohiyatini bilishga, moddiy va ma'naviy olamni uyg'unlashtirishga, tabiat va jamiyatni o'z maqsadlariga mos ravishda o'zgartirishga harakat qiladi. Ilm-fan va texnika insonning ma'naviy va moddiy ehtiyojlarini qondirish quroli, muhim vosita bo'lib hizmat qiladi. Inson yuksak ma'naviyat tufayligina o'z ehtiyojlarini madaniy shakllarda oqilona va to'laroq qoldirish imkoniga ega bo'ladi.

Jamiyatning ma'naviy hayotiga olamni tushunish, jamiyat va inson tug'risidagi qarashlar, nazariyalar, ta'limotlar, g'oyalar, mafkura, ijtimoiy ong shakllari, ta'lim-tarbiya, ahborot vositalari, madaniyat, ilm-fan muassasalari va boshqalar kiradi.

Jamiyatning moddiy va ma'naviy hayotini boshqarish, kishilar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni tartibga solishda turli siyosiy institutlar (davlat, siyosiy partiyalar, tashkilotlar, turli uyushmalar) muhim o'rin tutadi. Jamiyatni boshqarishning siyosiy-huquqiy jihatlari ham muhimdir. Kishilar tamonidan siyosiy va huquqiy bilimlarning chuqur o'zlashtirilishi jamiyatning barqaror yashashi va rivojlanishida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Jamiyat rivoji, kishilarning moddiy va ma'naviy ehtiyojlari qondirilishida mehnat, mulk va mehnatning ijtimoiy taqsimlanishi beqiyos ahamiyatga ega. Mehnatning kishilarning qobiliyatiga qarab ijtimoiy taqsimlanishi natijasida muayyan kasb-kor bilan shug'ullanadigan toifalar, guruh, qatlam va sinflar vujudga keladi va ular jamiyat strukturasi o'ziga hos o'rin egalaydi, jamiyat taraqqiyotiga muayyan hissa qo'shadi.

Xolbuki, jamiyatning tub mohiyati uni tashkil etuvchi inson mohiyati bilan uzviy bog‘liq. Xuddi inson tanasini uning ruhidan ajratib bo‘lmagani singari, jamiyatning moddiy va ma’naviy jihatlarini ham bir-biridan ajratish va ularning birini ikkinchisidan ustun qo‘yish mantiqqa ziddir. Prezident Islom Karimov asarlarida jamiyatning moddiy va ma’naviy manfaatlarini uyg‘unlashtirish ijtimoiy taraqqiyot asosi ekani ta’kidlangan. Inson ma’naviyatini yuksaltirish orqaligina iqtisodiy rivojlanishga erishish mumkin. Shuning uchun ham xozirgi davrda aholi ma’naviyatini yuksaltirishga, milliy g‘oya va mafkura asoslarini shakllantirishga katta e’tibor berilyapti. Zero, kishilar iqtisodiy jihatdan qashshoq bo‘lgani uchun ilmsiz bo‘lmaydi, balki, aksincha — ilmsiz bo‘lgani uchun qashshoq bo‘ladi. Suning uchun yurtimizda xalq ma’naviyatini yuksaltirish orqali iqtisodiy farovonlikni ta’minlashga katta e’tibor berilyapti. Jamiyatning vujudga kelishi Kishilarni oila bo‘lib, jamoa bo‘lib uyushishga nima majbur qilgan, degan masala qadim zamonlardanoq ulug‘ mutafakkirlar e’tiborini jalb etgan. Bu masalani diniy tushunish — uni ilohiy kuch, xudo bilan bog‘lab izohlashdir.

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Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati;

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FAN VA INNOVATSIYA - 3

(Ilmiy-uslubiy to‘plam)

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